

Further studies on varieties GMR-2 (IET2885) and Rasi (IET1444), which were in insecticidal trials, showed more than 30% incidence on some treatments. These varieties were late sown and flowered late. When the same varieties were early sown and thus flowered early, they were not at all infected. This indicates that the time of flowering has some influence on disease incidence. ■

Varietal resistance to tungro

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Tungro virus disease first appeared in Tanjore district, Tamil Nadu, in 1978. In the 1979 thaladi season, some devastated fields of tungro-affected paddy were plowed under. The disease appears starting in the early kuruvai season and damage becomes severe in late kuruvai, samba, and thaladi. To select tungro-resistant varieties, observations were made in 3 sets (6 entries/set) of plantings made in kuruvai (6 plantings in Jun-Jul), samba (2 plantings, Oct), and thaladi (6 plantings, Oct-Nov). Among the 18 varieties (see table), TKM9 was best for kuruvai; CR1009, C025, and AD3488 for samba; and Ponni for thaladi. ■

Sources of varietal resistance to rice tungro virus. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Rice tungro virus (%)
<i>Kuruvai</i>	
ADT31	48.4
TKM9	13.8
AS3704	26.6
PL29	22.9
AD8991	48.9
AD6120	22.1
<i>Samba</i>	
C025	10.0
CO40	63.6
NLR9672	56.1
CR1009	9.5
AD7496	54.6
AD3488	15.3
<i>Thaladi</i>	
ASD15	27.8
ADT32	30.0
ADT35	19.9
IR34	16.0
Ponni	8.2
AD9408	20.8

Fake smut and bunt diseases in IRON entries

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In 1979 kharif, the natural incidence of false smut *Ustilaginoidea virens* Cke. (Takahashi) and bunt *Tilletia barclayana* Bref. (Sacc. & Syd.) diseases was observed in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) trial at CRRI. The diseases occurred on 11 of 345 entries. The infected panicles and grains per panicle were counted from

randomly selected plants of each of the 11 entries (see table).

The maximum false smut infection (22%) was in CR1022; that of bunt (12%) was in B541B-PN-58-5-3-1. The maximum number of false smut-infected grains (1-6) was in CR1013.

Most of the entries flowered in late October. One week before and after flowering the maximum/minimum temperature was 33°/24° C; relative humidity was 88-95%, and sunshine hours, about 9-10. Rain fell on only 1 day during the period. The crop was irrigated when necessary. ■

Occurrence of false smut and bunt diseases in entries of the International Rice Observational Nursery at CRRI, Cuttack, Orissa, India.

Entry	Plant infection (%)	Infected grains (no./panicle)
False smut.		
CR1022 (Jagannath natural cross)	22	1-2
CR1016 (Waikoku/T90(40))	20	1-2
CR1013 (Jagannath natural cross)	16	1-6
IET6080 (RP894-15-2-1-1) CR44-35/W12708	16	1-3
IET6426, CRM9-3633-18, GEB24 mutant	8	1-4
IET6056 (RP894-61-1-3-7-2) CR44-35/W12708	4	1-2
IET6496 (R22-2-10.1) IRI/Sigadis	2	0-1
BW100 (H501/Sel. 306)	2	1-2
BW78-7 (H501/Sel. 306)	2	1-2
Bunt		
B541B-PN-58-5-3-1, Politai-I/IR1108-2	12	1-3
B2360-8-5-L-R-4-3, IR2180-2/IR2178-1	6	1-3

Records of heavy attack of bunt and false smut of rice

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Although bunt [*Tilletia barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. & Syd. = *Neovossia horrida* (Tak.) Padwick & Khan] and false smut [*Claviceps virens* (Cke.) Sakurai ex Nakata = *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Tak.] are widespread diseases of

rice in Assam, they are considered minor because they affect only a few grains. With the introduction of new cultivars and application of fertilizers, occurrences of the diseases are, however, on the increase. Two unusually heavy occurrences in the Rice Experimental Station at Titabar and the surrounding areas in 1964 and 1965 are reported (Table 1, 2). The information gives the average percentage of infected grains of the infected panicles only and does not

Table 1. Infected grains due to bunt and false smut (alone or combined) on infected panicles, Assam, India, 1964.

Disease	Infected panicles (no.)	Total no. of grain	Total no. of affected grain	Affected grain (%)
Bunt	19	3608	1239	34.21
False smut	7	1298	473	36.44
Bunt + false smut	2	329	188	57.14